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**FEATURES OF MICRO-CIRCULATION DISTURBANCES ON THE
BACKGROUND OF HEMO-RHEOLOGICAL CHANGES DURING THE
DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOXIC HYPOXIA**

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Abstract: The experiments were carried out on 145 white rats of a mixed population with an initial weight of 150-200 g contained in vivarium on a normal laboratory diet. The aim of this work was to evaluate and change the rheological properties of blood in experimental hypoxic conditions. The results showed that in acute hypoxia there are sharp violations of the physical properties of erythrocyte membranes, the severity of which, depending on its genesis.

Keywords: hypotension, microcirculation, hemorheology, pathogenesis, experiment, disorder

INTRODUCTION

The problem of oxygen starvation of biological systems continues to be the focus of attention of researchers. This is due to the fact that hypoxia is a leading factor in the occurrences and developments of many pathological processes associated mainly with impaired functions of the blood, circulatory and respiratory systems [1, 2, 8, 15, 19, 20].

Modern ideas about the mechanisms of pathological changes in hypoxic conditions are based on experimental and clinical data. In this aspect, the study of hypoxia of critical conditions is of great importance, which is a complex multilateral

biological phenomenon that occurs as a result of disturbances in the activity of various organs and systems of the body.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In recent decades, the problem of hypoxia has developed intensively in various directions [3, 4, 7, 9, 11]. At the same time, along with indisputable successes, a number of issues that are fundamental in nature and require an in-depth methodological analysis have been clearly identified.

Various aspects of the hypoxic state were studied with the primary study of the function of external respiration, respiratory failure, and arterial oxygenation [5, 6, 10].

However, in most cases hypoxia is formed on almost all parts of the body's vital activity and on all levels of oxygen transport from the alveoli to the cell, which represents a change in the essence of all body functions. That is why the assessment of hypoxia, as a clinical phenomenon, requires the study of many body functions.

Modern methods for studying the manifestations of hypoxia, unfortunately, do not allow obtaining comprehensive information about the essence of physiological events occurring in the body. Understanding hypoxia, its pathogenesis and clinical essence is impossible without a simultaneous study of the processes occurring in the lungs, blood, micro-circulatory component of oxygen transport and the state of tissue metabolism.

The development of hypoxia is accompanied not only by an increase in energy imbalance, but also by structural and functional damage to cells and tissues, changes in the reactivity of blood vessels, a disturbance in their nutrition, and sharp violations of the rheological properties of blood [4, 12, 13]. These disorders lead to altered functions of vital organs with high metabolic activity, characterized by abundant blood supply and sensitive to oxygen starvation. Therefore, it is of great scientific interest to conduct a comprehensive study of the rheological properties of blood and the state of microcirculation of internal organs (liver, kidneys, and pancreas) to deepen the understanding of the pathogenesis of hypoxia [14].

According to some authors, during the first hours of hypoxic hypoxia, the alkaline reserve changes little; there is only a decrease in pCO₂ due to hyperventilation,

followed by an increase in blood pH. After a few hours, the alkaline reserve begins to decrease, and the degree of its decrease depends on the severity of the hypoxic state [15, 18]. The authors found in the terminal stage of hypoxic hypoxia a decrease in alkaline reserve to 8.8 vol %. The accumulation of carbon dioxide leads to the expansion of arterioles and capillaries, however, Shvets D.A., [16] express doubt that carbon dioxide actually increases blood flow, since there is a stimulation of respiration.

Studies to study the effect of hypoxia on the cardiovascular system were undertaken with the aim of accumulating factual material and elucidating the mechanisms of hemodynamic reactions. The main results of these studies can be summarized as follows. A short stay at high altitude is accompanied by an increase in heart rate and minor changes in systolic blood pressure. Increased blood circulation due to increased heart rate starts from a height of 2000 m, slowly increases to 7000 m, and then develops faster, and it is usually pronounced in untrained persons, whereas in trained people, adaptation is mainly carried out by increasing the stroke volume of the heart. At an altitude of about 5000 m and higher, disorganization in the activity of the cardiovascular system is observed, the strength of the heartbeat decreases, but the increase in heart rate can continue. With the ineffectiveness of compensatory reactions that enhance the activity of the circulatory apparatus, redistribution of blood and centralization of blood circulation, maintaining normal blood flow in vital organs such as the brain and heart are of great importance [7, 17].

Purpose of the study. The aim of this work was to evaluate and change the rheological properties of blood in experimental hypoxic conditions.

Material and research methods. The experiments were carried out on 145 white rats of a mixed population with an initial weight of 150-200 g contained in vivarium on a normal laboratory diet.

Hypoxic hypoxia was induced by placing rats in a pressure chamber SPT-200 Vaccum-DRIER. Animals were kept in a pressure chamber at an altitude of 9000 m for 3 hours. Studies were carried out at 1, 3, 24, 96 hours after reproduction of hypoxia.

The physical state of erythrocyte membranes was evaluated by the electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells and the value of the "zeta" potential, sorption capacity, as well as electrical breakdown of the erythrocyte membrane.

To determine the electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells, red blood cells used the micro-method of the Joiner. The principle of the method is that in a specially designed Goryaev's chamber, using a stopwatch, the speed of movement of each red blood cell in an electric field created by silver electrodes is measured under a microscope. The speed of 15 red blood cells in different directions is measured.

The sorption ability of red blood cells was determined by the method of A.A. Togaybaev et al. The optical density of the initial solution of the dye and after incubation with red blood cells was determined in the supernatant by the colorimetric method at a wavelength of 630 nm, in relation to physiological saline. The amount of absorbed dye (in %) was calculated by the formula. Electric breakdown of the erythrocyte membrane was determined by the method of Putvinsky A.V., et al.

One of the main indicators of the rheological properties of blood viscosity (or fluidity) was determined according to the Copley method with modification. The shear rate of blood at a given viscosity was also calculated by the formula. Based on the obtained values, a dynamic viscosity curve was constructed.

Results and its discussion. The metabolic processes in the internal organs depend on the preservation of the structure and function of red blood cells, the most important of which is the transport of oxygen to organs and tissues.

Under the influence of various factors, the physical properties of the surface layer of erythrocytes change, their membrane becomes denser, and even the permeability of the erythrocyte membrane is often disrupted, which leads to a violation of its metabolism.

When studying the electrophoretic mobility of erythrocytes in animals of the intact group, it was revealed that it is $1.34 \pm 0.03 \text{ N / s / V / cm}$. The value of the "zeta" potential was $19.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ mV}$ (table 1.).

In animals, 1 hour after hypoxic hypoxia, the electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells and their zeta potential decrease by 14.2% and 23.2%, respectively, compared with the intact group of animals. After 3 hours, the decrease is 29.2% and 35, 6%. And after 24 hours - these indicators gradually increased compared to the previous period. By 98 hours these parameters returned to normal. Consequently, hypoxic hypoxia leads to a decrease in the electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells and their "zeta" potential. The largest changes are normal, while observed 3 hours after hypoxic exposure.

Table 1

Indicators of electrophoretic mobility (electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells) and "zeta" potential of the membrane of red blood cells in hypoxic hypoxia

Study groups	Electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells (/c/v/cv)	Zeta potential (mV)
Intact	1,34±0,02	19,4±0,03
1 hour	1,15±0,01	14,9±1,44*
3 hours	0,95±0,09*	12,5±1,39*
24 hours	1,10±0,03*	17,8±1,98*
96 hours	1,28±0,07	18,8±1,63

Note: * - The results are reliable in relation to intact g. (P <0.05)

Considering that the electrophoretic mobility of red blood cells depends on the charge of their membranes, and a change in charge can lead to an increase in their sorption ability, the latter was also studied in the indicated terms after hypoxic exposure.

Based on the experiments conducted in an intact group of animals, it was found that white rat red blood cells absorb from a 0.025% methylene blue solution to $26.2 \pm$

2.3% of the dye. The data obtained are stable, in no animal the indicators of sorption ability of erythrocytes did not go beyond the above values.

The results of changes in the sorption capacity of red blood cells during hypoxic hypoxia in white rats depending on the duration of the studies are shown in Table 2. As can be seen, the highest indicators of sorption ability of red blood cells during hypoxic hypoxia were observed in the group of animals studied 1 hour after the induced hypoxic effect and an increase in sorption ability erythrocytes was 86.6% compared with the intact group of animals, and after 3 hours by 67.9%, respectively. 24 hours after the experiment, the sorption capacity of red blood cells decreases compared to previous periods, but remains significantly increased compared to the control. And after 98 hours, the sorption capacity of red blood cells was almost normal.

The results of the study of electrical breakdown of the erythrocyte membrane in white rats with hypoxic hypoxia are shown in table 3. In animals of the intact group, the value of this indicator was 70.1 ± 0.8 mV.

Table 2

Change in the sorption ability of red blood cells (sorption ability of red blood cells) with hypoxic hypoxia

Study groups	(M ± m)
Intact	26,2±0,93
1 hour	48,9±1,04*
3 hours	44,0±1,31*
24 hours	30,1±0,88*
96 hours	28,1±0,77

Note: * - The results are reliable in relation to intact gr (P <0.05)

Table 3

Indicators of electrical breakdown of the erythrocyte membrane in hypoxic hypoxia

Study groups	(M ± m)
Intact	70,1±1,55
1 hour	78,3±4,31
3 hours	103,4±5,85*
24 hours	82,5±4,16*
96 hours	74,6±4,43

Note: * - The results are reliable in relation to intact gr (P <0.05)

1 hour after hypoxic hypoxia, the electrical breakdown of the membrane increased by 11.6% compared with the intact group. After 3 hours, it increased by 47.6%. After 24 and 96 hours, the increase compared with the intact group was 16.2 and 6.4%, respectively, compared with the intact group, which indicates a tendency to recovery.

Therefore, studies have shown that hypoxic hypoxia is characterized by a violation of the permeability of erythrocyte membranes and the most pronounced increase in the permeability of the erythrocyte membrane for ions is observed after 3 hours of hypoxic exposure.

Thus, our studies have shown that with hypoxic hypoxia, the properties of the membranes of peripheral blood erythrocytes undergo a sharp change. These changes lead to a decrease in the elasticity of the membrane, a change in the electric charge of the membrane of blood cells, in connection with which the saturation of red blood cells with oxygen, as well as the processes of dissociation and oxygen transfer to other cells are disturbed.

Such inferior red blood cells, passing through the capillaries merge with each other, aggregation and adhesion occur, which cause an increase in blood viscosity.

The blood viscosity in animals was determined after 1, 3, 24, 96 hours, as well as when the pressure applied to the blood flow: 2, 4, 8, 12, 16 millimeter of water. The

results of changes in blood viscosity in white rats with hypoxic hypoxia depending on the duration of the experiment and blood pressure are shown in table 4.

In the intact group of animals, it was found that blood viscosity at a pressure of 2 millimeter of water is 5.0 ± 0.42 pascal-second, and at 16 millimeters of water is $3,81 \pm 0,26$ pascal-second. In experimental animals, in the dynamics of the development of a hypoxic state, a significant increase in blood viscosity and a significant decrease in the shear rate during the study period at various hydrostatic pressures are noted.

Table 4

Indicators of blood viscosity and shear rate depending on the duration of hypoxic hypoxia

Study groups	2 millimeters of water		16 millimeters of water	
	viscosity	Shear rate	viscosity	Shear rate
Intact	$5,0 \pm 0,42$	$7,63 \pm 0,08$	$3,8 \pm 0,25$	$76,5 \pm 0,27$
1 час	$6,2 \pm 0,13^*$	$4,55 \pm 0,18^*$	$4,3 \pm 0,14^*$	$73,6 \pm 2,9$
3 часа	$9,3 \pm 0,26^*$	$3,97 \pm 0,13^*$	$6,5 \pm 0,27^*$	$50,7 \pm 2,2^*$
24 часа	$7,5 \pm 0,16^*$	$6,84 \pm 0,18^*$	$5,1 \pm 0,12^*$	$69,4 \pm 1,2^*$
96 часов	$5,8 \pm 0,31$	$7,35 \pm 0,35$	$4,2 \pm 0,37$	$75,6 \pm 2,8$

Note: * - The results are reliable in relation to intact gr (P <0.05)

In hypoxic hypoxia, blood viscosity after 1 hour at a minimum pressure increased by 24%, and at a maximum exceeds the value of intact animals by 13,1%.

It was found that 3 hours after hypoxic exposure, the severity of these processes increases and the studied parameters at minimum and maximum applied pressures increase by 86 and 71,5% compared to the intact group, and by 50 and 51,1% compared to the previous period respectively.

After 24 hours, the severity of changes compared with the previous period decreases slightly: an increase in viscosity at the minimum and maximum applied pressures is 19.4 and 21.6%, but at the same time, in relation to the intact group of

animals at a minimum pressure, the blood viscosity remains high 50 %, and with a maximum of 34.2%.

In the subsequent period - after 96 hours, the tendency to decrease in viscosity at minimum and maximum applied pressures continues. So, in relation to the intact group of animals, at a minimum pressure, blood viscosity remains increased by 16% and at a maximum pressure of 10.5%, which indicates the preservation of blood hypercoagulation.

The shear rate of blood in the intact group of animals at a minimum pressure was $7.65 + 0.08 \text{ C}^{-1}$, and at a maximum pressure of $76.5 + 0.27 \text{ C}^{-1}$.

It is noted that already 1 hour after hypoxic exposure at a minimum pressure, the shear rate of blood decreases by 32.5%, and at a maximum of 35.7%. 3 hours after the experiment, the severity of these changes increases at the minimum and maximum applied pressures; by 48.0 and 43.8% in relation to the intact group of animals. One day after hypoxic exposure, an increase in shear rate is observed - at a minimum pressure of 72.2% compared with the previous period, and at a maximum pressure of 36.8%, respectively. 96 hours after the hypoxic state, the shear rate at minimum and maximum pressures continues to increase compared to the previous period and almost returns to the initial level.

Thus, the results obtained indicate that with hypobaric hypoxia, the most pronounced changes are observed after 3 hours, and by the end of the experiment tend to recover.

The value of blood viscosity at minimum pressure was higher than that at maximum pressure and high shear rates.

A decrease in the rate of shear of the blood and an increase in its viscosity will certainly affect the state of the vessels of various organs, the functional failure of which can lead to stagnation of blood and the development of organ hypoxia. Given this, in the following we investigated the state of micro-circulation of internal organs.

CONCLUSION

1. In acute hypoxia, there are sharp violations of the physical properties of erythrocyte membranes, the severity of which depends on its genesis: - hypoxic hypoxia causes changes that normalize by 96 hours of the post-hypoxic period.

2. Acute hypoxia leads to a violation of the permeability of erythrocyte membranes, the degree of which depends on the type of hypoxia. With hypoxic hypoxia, slight changes are observed.

3. Acute hypoxia is accompanied by severe violations of the rheological properties of blood; hypoxic hypoxia was pronounced to persist for a long time.

REFERENCES

[1]. Андриенко, А.В. Нарушения гемореологии при ДВС-синдроме и их коррекция плазмаферезом: монография / А.В. Андриенко, В. Г. Лычев, В. Усынин. - Германия : LAP LAMBERT Acad. Publ., 2013. - 144 с.

[2]. Voronina T.A. (2016) The role of hypoxia in stroke and convulsive states. Antihypoxants. FSBSI "Zakusov Institute of Pharmacology", Moscow, Russia For citation: Reviews on Clinical Pharmacology and Drug Therapy. Vol. 14, No. 1. - pp. 63-70. (In Russ)

[3]. Goldberg E.D., Dygay A.M., Zyuzkov G.N. (2006) The mechanisms of regulation of the blood system in oxygen deficiency and the participation of neural stem cells in adaptation to hypoxia // Bulletin of Siberian medicine, No. 2. – pp. 43-51.

[4]. Hypoxia. Adaptation, pathogenesis, clinic / Ed. Yu.L. Shevchenko. – St. Petersburg.: ELBI-SPb. LLC, 2000. – p. 384.

[5]. Грин, Д. Геморрагические заболевания и синдромы = Fast Facts Bleeding Disorders / Д. Грин, К. А. Ладлем; пер. с англ.; под ред. О. В. Сомоновой. - Москва: Практическая медицина, 2014. - 132 с.

[6]. Дементьева, И. И. Патология системы гемостаза / И. И. Дементьева, М. А. Чарная, Ю. А. Морозов. - Москва : ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2011. - 288 с.

[7]. Zinchuk V.V., Gatsura S.V., Glutkina N.V. (2016) Correction of the oxygen-transporting function of blood in the pathology of the cardiovascular system // Monograph. State Medical University. – p. 312.

[8]. Zyuzkov G.N. (2003) The mechanisms of hematological changes in the post-hypoxic period. Bulletin of RAMS, No. 1 (107). – pp. 20-23.

[9]. Комлев В.Л., Ларичев А.Б., Муравьев А.В. Гематологические и гемореологические показатели у больных флегмонами челюстно-лицевой области: влияние комплексного лечения с реамберином // Современные проблемы науки и образования. – 2013. – № 4.

[10]. Кручинина М.В., Абдуллаева П.А., Громов А.А., Баум В.А., Генералов В.М., Генералов К.В., Кручинин В.Н., Рыхлицкий С.В. Возможности оценки степени тяжести гемореологических нарушений у лиц с артериальной гипертензией // Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований. – 2018. – № 6. – С. 75-84.

[11]. Левин Г.Я., Поповичева А. Н., Соснина Л. Н. Гемореологические нарушения у детей после термической травмы // Патологическая физиология и экспериментальная терапия. 2020. Т. 64. № 3. С. 74-79.

[12]. Lukyanova L.D. (2000) Modern problems of hypoxia // Vestnik RAMS. № 9. - pp. 3-12. (In Russ)

[13]. Lukyanova LD. (2004) Mitochondrial dysfunction as a typical pathological process, the molecular mechanism of hypoxia. Problems of hypoxia: molecular, physiological and medical aspects / Ed. L.D. Lukyanova, I.B. Ushakova. – Moscow. Sources. - pp. 8-50. (In Russ)

[14]. Titov D.V. (2012) Microcirculatory, hemoreological and urodynamic disturbances in children with hyperactive urocyt. Bulletin of Siberian Medicine. 11(2): - pp. 77-79. (In Russ.)

[15]. Ushakov I.B. (2004) Hypoxic mechanisms of combined effects // Problems of hypoxia: molecular, physiological and medical aspects / Ed. L.D. Lukyanova, I.B. Ushakova. – Moscow. Sources. – pp. 297–397. (In Russ)

[16]. Shvets D.A. (1996) Pathogenetic substantiation of the use of helium-oxygen therapy in the correction of hemorheological and autonomic dysfunctions in hypoxic conditions of obstructive-respiratory origin // Diss., Candidate of Medical Sciences. – Moscow. – pp. 136.

[17]. In'tAnker P.S., Noort W.A., Scherjon S.A. et al. (2003) Mesenchymal stem cells in human second-trimester bone marrow, liver, lung, and spleen exhibit a similar immunophenotype but a heterogenous multilineage differentiation potential // *Haematologica*. Vol. 88. – pp. 845-852.

[18]. Li C., Jackson R.M. (2002) Reactive species mechanisms of cellular hypoxia-reoxygenation injury // *Am. J. Physiol. Cell Physiol.* (USA). Vol. 282. № 2. – pp. 227-241.

[19]. Fisher M. Hemorheological factors in cerebral ischemia / M. Fisher [et al.] // *Stroke*. — Vol. 22, N 39. — P. 1164–1169.

[20]. Lip G. Y. Sequential alterations in haemorheology, endothelial dysfunction, platelet activation and thrombogenesis in relation to prognosis following acute stroke / G. Y. Lip[et al.] // *The West Birmingham Stroke Project. Blood Coagul Fibrinolysis*. — 2010 Jun. — Vol. 13 (4). — P. 339–347.